

THE INFLUENCE GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION IN MEDAN: INSIGHT FROM SEM-PLS ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the extent to which the procurement of renewable energy and the effectiveness of its use affect the increase in consumer purchase decisions in Medan City through the creation of green marketing strategies as an intervening variable. The subject of this study is consumers or residents of Medan City who use green energy, where the variables in this study are independent variables, namely renewable energy procurement and effectiveness of use, dependent variables, namely variables that increase consumer purchase decisions and intervening variables are variables that create green marketing strategies. The results of the data analysis were used using SEM analysis using SMART PLS 4.0 software. The data collection technique with questionnaires, as well as observation. The research method uses a quantitative descriptive method of data analysis using *the structural equation model* (SEM) method, where the results of data processing using the SEM method are carried out with the PLS 4.0 application. From the results of the study, the existing conclusion, namely the partial use of renewable energy and the effectiveness of its use affect the increase in consumer purchase decisions and affect the creation of green marketing strategies. Simultaneously, the variable variable of renewable energy use and the effectiveness of use have an effect on the improvement of consumer purchase decisions through the variable of creating a green marketing strategy as an intervening variable. The more the use of renewable energy increases, the more effective the use of renewable energy will be to prevent the reduction of carbon emissions and climate change, so that the need for renewable energy will create an effective green marketing strategy that will cause an increase in consumer purchasing decisions to use renewable energy products.

Keywords: Green Marketing Strategy, Use of Renewable Energy, Effectiveness of Use, Consumer Purchase Decisions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Green marketing is related to the emphasis on the creation of renewable energy through green energy marketing, where there are green plants that are useful and able to create clean and renewable energy called green energy, where green energy is very important for the sustainability of nature, especially to prevent the reduction of ozone which is increasingly eroded due to fossil energy that tends to pollute the air (Tsai, Bay Hsuan, 2020).

Green marketing through the procurement of green and clean energy, as well as new renewables, is motivated by the increase in the earth's temperature and climate change which tends to increase the temperature on the earth's surface, where to prevent this, it is necessary to reduce carbon emissions that can be done by reducing carbon emissions (Al Mamun, Abdullah, 2023).

Based on the ratification of the 2020 Paris agreement that every country must be able to reduce carbon emissions by 20% per year, where increasing carbon emissions will actually increase the earth's temperature getting hotter, while increasing the frequency and intensity of heat waves can cause serious health problems such as dehydration, heat stroke, and death (Bahl, Abhishek, 2023).

Rising temperatures can cause Sea level rise due to melting Arctic ice can cause flooding in coastal areas, damage property, and drive millions of people from their homes. Another impact of this increase in temperature has an impact on the Agriculture sector with the procurement of green plants that often fail to harvest due to rain and dry out due to drought, making temperature rise a threat in itself (Duong, Cong Doanh, Nguyen, Thanh Hieu and Nguyen, 2023).

In the procurement of renewable energy through green energy, every country must design and produce an environmentally friendly product, where products are made with environmentally friendly materials and can be recycled and use renewable energy or renewable energy (Vangeli, Anastas, 2023)

This can have an impact on reducing existing carbon emissions through green marketing strategies carried out in order to create clean, environmentally friendly and non-pollutant energy (Kumar, Anil, Prakash & and Kumar, 2021).

In increasing the use of renewable energy, the production process uses technologies and practices that reduce pollution and energy consumption, as well as waste that contains radioactive materials and pollutants that can damage the skin and can harm human health (Berki-Kiss, Daniel and Menrad, 2022).

The use of renewable energy can be effective if its use is carried out carefully and carefully, and the materials are able to overcome climate problems, as well as protect humans from solar radiation that penetrates due to ozone erosion on the earth (Harorli, Emre and Ercis, 2023).

Consumers basically need something new, products that are adaptive and protective, and beneficial for environmental conservation, where these protective products are always the target of consumers and make consumers interested in using these products, so extra strict efforts are needed to persuade consumers to decide to buy products that are beneficial for health and also protection from global warming and climate change (Olson, 2022).

For consumers who can afford it, they will be happy to consume and use renewable energy products, besides being able to protect from global warming, renewable energy can also be used to clean something, such as cleaning iron products and vehicle engines, as well as cleaning the cauldron when finishing cooking are some important benefits for consumers who do need clean and environmentally friendly products (Mungoni, Ernest, Nyagadza, Brighton and Hove, 2023).

Consumers who use renewable energy must be able to understand its use appropriately so that it is effective and efficient, where this renewable energy must be used as effectively as possible in order to reduce carbon emissions, as triggered by the Paris agreement of 20% per year, where this agreement is binding on the countries that originate the Paris agreement including Indonesia, so that it can be said that the effectiveness of the use of renewable energy can be easily done if according to its measure and can reduce carbon emissions, as triggered in the Paris Agreement (Boccia, Flavio and Tohidi, 2024).

The effectiveness of the use of renewable energy in accordance with the standards set by the world creates something needed to be able to use it simultaneously and widely. This has an impact on the increasing demand for renewable energy which makes renewable energy increase in demand (Ye, Fei, 2021).

The more effective the use of renewable energy, the more strategies will be allocated to create the right energy, so that a strong effort is needed by stakeholders, especially the Government and also appointed entrepreneurs to realize green energy and the use of renewable energy (Amalia, Firdia Rizky and Darmawan, 2023).

The increasing use and effectiveness of the use of renewable energy has triggered an increasing strategy launched by several entrepreneurs to create products through the implementation of green energy strategies, where this green energy can be obtained from environmentally friendly products that are very effective and useful for environmental sustainability (Dash, Ganesh, Kiefer, Kip and Paul, 2021)

Medan is one of the areas with a high level of pollution in Indonesia, where there are still some people who do not realize how important the use of renewable energy is for the benefit of the environment and also for the sustainability of the city of Medan which is free from pollution and damage to the city's environment. Of the 2,494,512 people in Medan City, only 4% use environmentally friendly products, where the people of Medan City are still used to fossil energy which tends to pollute the air that disturbs public health.

The use of renewable energy is very small, so it has an impact on the decrease in the effectiveness of the use of renewable energy with an increase in air pollution in the range of 52 AQI-US which is high compared to last month of 48 AQS, where low effectiveness will have an impact on the ability to implement green marketing strategies and make 4% of existing consumers decide not to be interested in buying renewable energy products.

Problem Formulation

The formulation of the problem that emerged from this study is how the variable of renewable energy procurement and the effectiveness of its use affect the improvement of consumer purchase decisions in Medan City through the creation of a green marketing strategy as an intervening variable.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the extent to which the procurement of renewable energy and the effectiveness of its use affect the increase in consumer purchase decisions in Medan City through the creation of green marketing strategies as an intervening variable.

Originality of Research

The subject of this study is consumers or residents of Medan City who use green energy, where the variables in this study are independent variables, namely renewable energy procurement and effectiveness of use, dependent variables, namely variables that increase consumer purchase decisions and intervening variables are variables that create green marketing strategies.

The results of the data analysis were used using SEM analysis using SMART PLS 4.0 software. The data collection technique with questionnaires, as well as observation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Renewable Energy Procurement

Renewable energy procurement is the process of developing and using renewable and inexhaustible energy sources, such as solar, wind, water, and biomass. Renewable energy is very important in efforts to reduce dependence on fossil fuels, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and maintain environmental sustainability (Ismail, Ismail Juma, Amani & and Changalima, 2023).

Renewable energy procurement is an important step towards a cleaner and more sustainable future. With the right investments and policy support, renewable energy can play a key role in meeting global energy needs while protecting the environment (Gustavo, Jorge Ubirajara, 2021).

Indicators of the use of renewable energy are:

1. Percentage of the amount of renewable energy used
2. Renewable energy installed capacity
3. Renewable energy production
4. Reduction of carbon emissions from the use of renewable energy (Mehrez, Hassen Khadija, Khemeera, Habib & Medavesh, 2023)

Effectiveness of Using Renewable Energy

The effectiveness of the use of renewable energy can be measured by considering a variety of factors that include economic, environmental, technological, and social (Cabeza-Ramírez, L. Javier, 2022). The more effective the use of renewable energy, the better the ability of renewable energy to support a 20% reduction in carbon emissions (Li, Lixu, 2021). The indicators of the effectiveness of the use of renewable energy include:

1. Improved economic performance
2. Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions
3. Improved environmental sustainability (Fraccascia, Luca, Ceccarelli & and Dangelico, 2023)

Consumer Purchasing Decisions

Consumer purchasing decisions are the processes that individuals or groups go through when selecting, purchasing, using, and evaluating goods or services to meet their needs and desires (Nekmahmood, MD, 2022). There are several factors that affect the decision to purchase products by consumers, namely psychological factors from within the consumer's body, social factors from the influence of family members, personal factors, cultural factors or beliefs and economic factors (Pandey, Mithilesh and Yadav, 2023). The indicators of consumer purchase decisions are:

1. Brand awareness level
2. Brand preferences
3. Purchase intent
4. Customer satisfaction (Alam, Mohammad Nurul, 2023)

Creation of Green Marketing Strategy

A green marketing strategy aims to promote a product or service in a way that demonstrates a commitment to environmental sustainability. This not only helps attract consumers who care about the environment but also strengthens the brand's image as a socially responsible company (Zubair, Muhammad, 2020).

In implementing the green marketing strategy, we must identify the target market, conduct market segmentation mapping, create appropriate product designs and analyze the weaknesses, strengths, opportunities and challenges to the product marketing that will be carried out (Shanmugavel, Nagarajan and Micheal, 2022).

The indicators of the creation of a green marketing strategy are:

1. Green brand awareness
2. Green brand perception
3. Green product sales
4. Green customer loyalty (Bommenahalli Veerabhadrapa, Narendra Babu, Fernandes, Semila & Panda, 2023)

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the research is:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

1. Renewable energy procurement affects the increase in consumer purchasing decisions
2. The effectiveness of use has an effect on improving consumer purchase decisions
3. Renewable energy procurement has an effect on the creation of green marketing strategies

4. The effectiveness of use has an effect on the creation of green marketing strategies
5. The creation of a green marketing strategy has an effect on improving consumer purchase decisions
6. The procurement of renewable energy has an effect on increasing consumer purchasing decisions through initiatives to create green marketing strategies as an intervening variable
7. The effectiveness of use has an effect on increasing consumer purchasing decisions through the initiative to create a green marketing strategy as an intervening variable.

Research Methods

This research method was carried out using a quantitative descriptive method using method analysis *Structural Equation Model* (SEM), where according to (Dangelico, Rosa Maria, Alvino, Letizia and Fraccascia, 2022) SEM analysis is a statistical method used to test and measure the mutually influencing relationships between existing variables.

The population in this study is 99,781 residents of Medan City who consume renewable energy products, where the sampling method is carried out using the *Simple random sampling*, which according to (Dangelico, Rosa Maria, Alvino, Letizia and Fraccascia, 2022) sampling method using *Simple random sampling* is a sampling method in which each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected as part of the sample.

The number of samples taken can be done using the slovin formula as follows:

$n = N / (1 + Ne^2) = 99,781 / (1 + 99,781 \times 0.1^2) = 100 = 100$ residents of Medan City who consume renewable energy products.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research Methods

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4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Results

The output of the SEM test can be described through the following *Bootstrapping* diagram:

Figure 2: *Bootstrapping Diagram*

Convergent Validity Analysis

(Dangelico, Rosa Maria, Alvino, Letizia and Fraccascia, 2022) states that the analysis *convergent validity* is a type of test that explains how valid the data is as a result of observation. The test results *convergent validity* In this study, it is as follows:

Table 1: *Convergent Validity Test*

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Use of Renewable Energy (x1)	PET 1	0,837
	PET 2	0,861
	PET 3	0,872
	PET 4	0,845
Effectiveness of Use (X2)	EP 1	0,862
	EP 2	0,754
	EP 3	0,832
Increased Consumer Purchase Decision (Y)	PKPK 1	0,840
	PKPK 2	0,855
	PKPK 3	0,874
	PKPK 4	0,865
Creation of Green Marketing Strategy (Z)	PSPH 1	0,885
	PSPH 2	0,766
	PSPH 3	0,815
	PSPH 4	0,890

Source: Results of Data Processing with PLS 3.0, 2024

The table above states that the data from each observation through the construct variable is valid and suitable for use.

Analysis of Average Variant Extracted (AVE)

(Dangelico, Rosa Maria, Alvino, Letizia and Fraccascia, 2022) stated that the AVE test is one of the test results aimed at determining the assessment of whether the data is appropriate or not. The test results *Average Variant Extracted* (AVE) is in the following table:

Table 2: AVE Test

Variable	AVE
Use of Renewable Energy (x1)	0,830
Effectiveness of Use (X2)	0,874
Increased Consumer Purchase Decision (Y)	0,844
Creation of Green Marketing Strategy (Z)	0,864

Source: Data Processing Results with PLS 4.0, 2024

The table above describes the *Average Variant Extracted* (AVE) value greater than 0.5 which means that the model of the construction equation from the observation results is in accordance with the results.

Composite Reliability Analysis

According to(Dangelico, Rosa Maria, Alvino, Letizia and Fraccascia, 2022) Testing *Composite Reliability* It is an analysis to understand the existing data is very reliable or appropriate. This can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Composite Reliability Test

Variable	Composite Reliability
Use of Renewable Energy (x1)	0,886
Effectiveness of Use (X2)	0,821
Increased Consumer Purchase Decision (Y)	0,871
Creation of Green Marketing Strategy (Z)	0,852

Source: Data Processing Results with PLS 4.0, 2024

The table above states that *the composite reliability* value is greater than 0.6, where the existing data is appropriate or reliable.

Discriminant Validity Analysis

In confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) or structural equation modeling (SEM), the validity analysis of discrimination is how much the relationship between different construction equations occurs. The results of the Discriminant Validity analysis can be seen in the following Table 4:

Table 4: Discriminant Validity Analysis

	Improving Consumer Purchase Decisions Moderating Effect 1	Improving Consumer Purchase Decisions Moderating Effect 2	Improving Consumer Purchase Decisions Moderating Effect 3	Improving Consumer Purchase Decisions Moderating Effect 4
Use of Renewable Energy	.757	1.000	.757	.627
Effectiveness of Use	.664	.737	1.000	.727
Improved Consumer Purchase Decisions	.757	.786	.837	1.000
Creation of Green Marketing Strategy	1.000	.747	.667	.637

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the existing AVE value has significantly met the *Discriminant Validity* assumption.

Path Coefficient Testing

As for the *path coefficient test*, it can be found through the following table:

Table 5: R Square Test

Variable	R Square
Use of Renewable Energy (x1)	0,881
Effectiveness of Use (X2)	0,845
Increased Consumer Purchase Decision (Y)	0,865
Creation of Green Marketing Strategy (Z)	0,854

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2023

From the existing table, R Square variable of improving the quality of improving consumer purchase decisions can be explained by the variables of renewable energy use, effectiveness of use and initiative to create green marketing strategies by 86.5%, while the remaining 14.5% can be explained by other variables that are not in the study.

Hypothesis Test

The results of hypothesis testing can be seen through the following table:

Table 6: Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	Influence	T-Statistics	P-Value	Result
H1	The use of renewable energy to increase consumer purchasing decisions	5,615	0,000	Accepted
H2	The effectiveness of use on improving consumer purchasing decisions	6,144	0,001	Accepted
H3	The use of renewable energy towards the creation of green marketing strategies	4,324	0,002	Accepted
H4	The effectiveness of use on the creation of green marketing strategies	5.543	0,000	Accepted
H5	Creation of green marketing strategies towards improving consumer purchasing decisions	6,255	0,000	Accepted
H9	The use of renewable energy to increase consumer purchasing decisions through the creation of green marketing strategies as an intervening variable	4,424	0,000	Accepted
H10	The effectiveness of its use on improving consumer purchasing decisions through the creation of green marketing strategies as an intervening variable	3,617	0,000	Accepted

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2023

According to the table above, it can be concluded that partially, the variables of renewable energy use and effectiveness of use have an effect on increasing consumer purchase decisions and affect the creation of green marketing strategies. Simultaneously, the variable variable of renewable energy use and the effectiveness of use have an effect on the improvement of consumer purchase decisions through the variable of creating a green marketing strategy as an intervening variable.

Discussion

The Use of Renewable Energy Affects the Increase in Consumer Purchase Decisions

The results of the study stated that Use of renewable energy affecting the increase in consumer purchase decisions. This is in accordance with research (Cambodia, Shampi, Matar, Manita, & Gupta, 2023) which states that the use of renewable energy that is adaptive and able to ensure public protection will be able to improve the purchasing decision of consumers to use these products.

Effective Use Affects Improving Consumer Purchase Decisions

The results of the study explain that the effectiveness of use affects the increase in consumer purchase decisions. This is in line with research (Chou, Sheng Fang, 2020) which states that the more effective the use of renewable energy, the better and better it will protect the environment and make more consumer purchasing decisions using these products.

The Use of Renewable Energy Affects the Creation of Green Marketing Strategies

According to the results of the existing research Use of renewable energy affect the creation of green marketing strategies. This is in accordance with research (Dahlquist, 2021) which states that the better the use of renewable energy, the better the process of creating a green marketing strategy to the community that makes people interested in using these products to protect the environment.

The Effectiveness of Use Affects the Creation of Green Marketing Strategies

According to the results of existing studies, the variable of effectiveness of use affects Green Marketing Strategy Creation Initiative. This is in line with research (Syed, Tahir Abbas, Mehmood, Fahad and Qaiser, 2023) which states that the effective use of renewable energy will make the process of creating a green marketing strategy better and effective to attract customers to use environmentally friendly products.

The Creation of Green Marketing Strategies Affects the Increase in Consumer Purchase Decisions

The results of the study stated that the creation of a green marketing strategy had an effect on increasing consumer purchase decisions. This is in accordance with research (Prieto-Sandoval, Vanessa, Torres-Guevara, Luz Elba and García-Díaz, 2022) who explained that the creation of a green marketing strategy to consumers that is attractive will increase the purchase decision to use the product because of its benefits.

The Use of Renewable Energy Affects the Increase in Consumer Purchase Decisions through the Creation of Green Marketing Strategies as an Intervening Variable

The results of the study explain that the variable Use of renewable energy affects the improvement of consumer purchase decisions through the creation of a green marketing strategy as an intervening variable. This is in accordance with research (Ahmad, Wasim, 2023) who explained that the better use of renewable energy will create a desire to adopt a green marketing strategy in Ranakka to improve customers' decision to buy renewable energy products comprehensively.

Effectiveness of Use Affects Improving Consumer Purchase Decisions through the Creation of Green Marketing Strategies as an Intervening Variable

The results of the study explain that the variable Efficiency of use affects the improvement of consumer purchase decisions through the creation of a green marketing strategy as an intervening variable. This is in accordance with research (Li, Zhimin, 2021) which states that the effectiveness of the use of renewable energy will tend to create a green marketing strategy through certain segments in order to attract interest and increase consumer purchasing decisions for certain green economy products.

Implementation

The more the use of renewable energy increases, the more effective the use of renewable energy will be to prevent the reduction of carbon emissions and climate change, so that the need for renewable energy will create an effective green marketing strategy that will cause an increase in consumer purchasing decisions to use renewable energy products.

5. CONCLUSION

From the results of the study, the existing conclusion, namely the partial use of renewable energy and the effectiveness of its use affect the increase in consumer purchase decisions and affect the creation of green marketing strategies. Simultaneously, the variable of renewable energy use and the effectiveness of use have an effect on the improvement of consumer purchase decisions through the variable of creating a green marketing strategy as an intervening variable.

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